

BKOOOL CASE STUDY: THE INTEGRATION OF A PHYSICAL AND VIRTUAL EXPERIENCE THROUGH A SOCIAL NETWORK FOR SPORTS.

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ABSTRACT

Bkool is a newly established company whose purpose is to provide a service that allows sports fans to enjoy their hobby during the working days, in an indoor environment, but in a fun and motivating way. As a first development, *Bkool* launched to market a product that facilitates indoor cycling practice, by integrating a physical with a virtual experience. To perform this integration, the company has followed the principles of *IOP* methodology developed by the *IBV*. The monitoring methodology has helped to address the development of the system from the perspective of people, so diverse aspects have been considered, such as the need to emulate the physical experience of cycling, or the increase of recognition of a cycling community as a way to increase the motivation to continue sports practice.

Keywords: user experience, service design, innovation, virtual experience, *IOP* methodology.

INTRODUCTION

Bkool is a business initiative that comes from the perception by its advocates, that there was a business opportunity to launch a product that would enhance the experience of indoor cycling practice through social networks. To perform this idea, since *Bkool* always considered the human factor should take precedence over the technology, it was felt that *IBV* was the ideal partner to collaborate with the development of *Bkool* products.

The *IBV* is a technological center that focuses its activity on the development of products and services

from the perspective of people. Thus, the projects are always tackled analyzing the relationship between persons and the products they use, or the environment in which they are operated. As a result of this approach, the center has been developing in recent years a people driven innovation methodology, that is referred as *IOP* methodology (Sanchez, J., March, R. et al). This methodology brings together tools and techniques that facilitate the participation of people (users and professionals) in all phases of the development process in order to add value.

The methodology is based on people power to make a product become an innovation, as their purchasing decisions are the ultimate element that determines the success of a product when it gets into the market (Goodman R. and Pavón J.; Godin, B.).

Similarly, the methodology aims to go beyond the principles of *UCD* (User Centered Design, Raabe, P.), as it is proposed to involve people in all phases of the development process as a source of value creation. In this sense, although it is true that the *UCD* is based on people participation as a source of value in the development process through the application of tools from social research, as well as other disciplines such as ergonomics or usability, such participation focuses on the needs assessment phase and new uses, as well as the validation phase.

This paper presents the development work associated with the *Bkool* device for cycling practice. In order that the presentation of the work is consistent, in the first part of the document the core axes, that were defined to guide the development process, are detailed. Next, the work done to advance in the development of the device, following the general principles and *IOP* methodology is outlined. Finally, some general considerations as well as some current lines of

development for both the cycling device and the *Bkool* platform, are presented.

DEVELOPMENT CORE AXIS

Bkool is a social network for sports online, aimed at people who like sport as a way of leisure and testing one's limits (competition), and as a means for establishing social relationships. This platform of sport arises with the idea of combining physical experience that is felt in performing a sporting activity, with the virtual experience associated with navigating social networks. In fact, its creators define *Bkool* as a *web platform to sweat*.

The development of a device for cycling in *Bkool* should combine physical and virtual experience that aims to provide the platform, so it should be based on the following axes:

- People driven development (*IOP* methodology).
- Physical experience: the use of the device should allow indoor cycling, but emulating the sensory experience of outdoor cycling.
- Emotional experience: maintaining motivation through registration of physical progression, and belonging to a sports community.
- Usability: the connection of hardware in the digital platform should not be a barrier to any user.
- Training plans: build a model to create training plans, which uses as input variables from the biometric information of people, to miles covered per week, among others.

NEEDS AND OPPORTUNITIES

Once the core axes that should guide the cycling device development process were defined, the project followed with the *Detection of needs and opportunities* phase, as referred by the *IOP* methodology. The work done at this stage focused on identifying the profiles of users interested in *Bkool* cycling device. To make this identification, four *focus groups* in four different Spanish cities (Valencia, Zaragoza, Bilbao and Madrid) were conducted. As a result of this work, three different profiles of users were identified, as it is presented as follows:

- Competition and fitness improvement.
- Fitness maintenance and wellness.

- Leisure and personal relations.

In order to identify qualities and attributes of cycling device, defining which profile user of those of the identified was more appropriate for hosting the product launch, we conducted a survey distributed to 500 people in different cities of the Spanish territory. As a result of this survey, a customer profile that responded to the following definition was targeted: person under 38 years, outdoor sport practitioner only on weekends, that likes to compete and has internet access at home, and knows other sport systems to be used at home.

ANALYZE SOLUTIONS

The next phase of the *IOP* methodology is related to the generation of design solutions that meet the requirements defined for the product. For this purpose, a three day workshop was organized, in which different profiles of participants, lead users (Von Hippel, E.), designers and social researchers, were combined. As a result of these sessions it was determined that the system to best fit the requirements, from both the user and the *Bkool* experience, was a system comprising a roller brake, which is managed by an application, accessible through the web. The characteristics to be met by components of this system were defined as follows:

- *Bkool web*:
 - Storage of all information generated during the outdoor and indoor sessions
 - Generation of training plans tailored to each user, which are fed through the stored information.
 - Creation of a social network of users, characterized by their sport level.
- *Application available through the web*
 - Real routes of outdoor cycling, from mythical *big tours* stages, until those registered by the user.
 - Reproduction of real images associated with the routes.
 - Connection of multiple users in real time, performing the same route.
- *Roller brake*:
 - Sensations perceived by the user when starting the pedal should be

similar to those he feels when he goes out with the bike.

- The system should simulate specific aspects of travelling by bicycle as the transition that occurs to initiate a slope (inertia), or the effort decrease when traveling in the slipstream of another rider.
- Ease of installation and system connection.
- The difference in braking force between two rollers must be less than 5%.

In order to fulfill the defined requirements for roller brake, the development of a permanent magnet electromagnetic brake is proposed. This brake was equipped with a roll of small diameter (*Figure 1*), coated with a material of high coefficient of friction, which guarantees both the grasp of the bicycle wheel, and a high speed brake disk. This brake disc diameter was large compared with the roller, in order to increase the sensitivity of the permanent magnet brake.

Figure 1. Working prototype of the electromagnetic brake system.

The pedaling sensations of the prototype shown in Figure 1 were evaluated by three *lead users*, who

tested valuation of the system under constant slope, between 0 and 15% slope.

DESIGN AND MANUFACTURE

The design of the application accessible via the web has been addressed following the usability principles. Since the application must show actual images of the routes that the user follows, a system that generates the contents of the application (*Figure 2*) was developed. Similarly, a format for displaying the relative position of a user in the multi-game group was defined (*Figure 3*). The capability to view real-time position within the group let the user employ some roller brake utilities such as riding the slipstream of another cyclist.

Figure 3. Relative position of each user in a multiplayer session.

Once the braking concept was validated at the functional level, sketches to produce a roller that meets defined product specifications were generated. The proposals generated are shown in *Figure 4*. To select the alternative that best fits the needs of the project, a technique of alternatives selection was applied (*RGT*, Kelly, G.A.). For applying this technique, a multidisciplinary team of users took part.

Figure 4. Roller brake conceptual proposals.

The development of the product concept selected, led the design and manufacture of the roller brake shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Roller brake Bkool.

The generation of training plans required the development of a model that considers user biometric information. After an initial stress testing, and the weekly hours available for training, the model proposes a plan that is updated as the user logs the information relative to its outdoor and indoor outlets. For development of this model, collaboration with professional cycling coaches was required.

COMMERCIALIZATION

As a prelude to the commercialization of roller brakes, and since the system had to meet the functional requirements set, the system was tested by 300 users spread throughout the Spanish territory. This validation test began in November 2010 and lasted for three months. Since the braking force could vary up to 10% between two devices, due to the variability of the magnetic fields generated by magnets, all rollers must be factory calibrated. The validation test results allowed the adjustment of the parameters that control the operation of the roller brake, in order that the sensations transmitted by the roller simulate outdoor cycling practice.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The generation of training plans on the website allows *Bkool* users to evolve in their athletic progression, increasing motivation for practicing sport. The ability to compete in real time via the web (64 players) also increases motivation, as it allows the user to check their progress, displaying their achievements to the rest of the community. This capability to compete in real time that simulates riding outdoors is possible due to calibration of the roller, as users recognize the outcome of the meeting as valid. Similarly, additional functionalities such as the decrease in effort when a user places himself in the slipstream of another one, or the transition when there is a slope change, makes the simultaneous gameplay more attractive for users. Moreover, the possibility of logging the records of the outdoor sessions in the system, to complete the training plans, strengthens the integration of physical and virtual experience that *Bkool* aims to generate. Recently, *Bkool* has launched a free application for smartphones (Figure 6) that records all the outdoor session information in the terminal (from the biometric data to the topography of the session), facilitating the download directly from the web. Similarly, a new application that allows users to record their sessions with a *GPS outdoor camera*, and upload to the site to share with your community has been launched.

Figure 6. Bkool application for smartphone.

Meanwhile, *Bkool* is currently working on new applications that improve the indoor experience, including development of an application for riding in *gruppetta*, so it is possible to speak with each of the partners who share a session. For the development of these applications, the company follows the principles of the IOP methodology, gathering information from people who use their products in a systematic way. Similarly, *Bkool* is developing new devices, which enable to extend the physical and virtual integration to other sports like running or swimming.

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